

Infrared Investigations of β -Picoline-halogen Charge-transfer Complexes

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The infrared spectra (4 000 - 400 cm^{-1}) of β -pic- I_2 , β -pic- ICl , β -pic- IBr , β -pic- Br_2 and β -pic- BrCl charge-transfer complexes have been studied in a range of solvents. The solid β -pic- I_2 complex has been found to undergo solid state transformation 2β -pic- $\text{I}_2 \rightarrow (\beta$ -pic- $\text{I})^+ \text{I}_3^-$. In polar solvents all the complexes ionise.

But no evidence for ionisation have been found in non-polar solvents. Assuming a C_2 symmetry point group for these complexes all the observed bands have been assigned. The vibrations at 1 044 and 621 cm^{-1} of β -picoline have been found to be quite sensitive to complex formations. The effect of solvent and acceptor on these two vibrations have been discussed.

THE effect on vibrational spectra of halogens due to the formation of charge-transfer complexes with various donors have been the subject of many investigations^{1,2}. Contrary to this, very little work has been done on the vibrational spectra of the donors. The most intensely studied donor molecules are benzene³, trimethylamine⁴, pyridine⁵, dioxane⁶, and a few others. The vibrational frequencies of the benzene and dioxane molecules do not shift on complex formation except some change in intensities. But infrared spectra of trimethylamine and pyridine have been found to change remarkably. The β -picoline-halogen complexes have not been extensively studied. The infrared spectra of equimolar β -picoline-iodine solutions have been examined over a small frequency range around 1 000 cm^{-1} by Glusker and Thomson⁷ and they observed changes in the frequencies of a number of β -picoline bands providing evidence of complex formation. The far-infrared spectra of β -picoline- ICl have also been examined⁸. In this paper, the infrared spectra of β -picoline-halogens in the frequency range 4 000-400 cm^{-1} are presented in solutions of various solvents and also in mulls. The nature of the species present is discussed, the frequencies are assigned and the solvent and acceptor effects on the ring vibrations are also discussed.

Experimental

β -Picoline was dried over KOH and BaO for

several days and distilled under reduced pressure. Iodine (AnalaR) was resublimed and dried over P_2O_5 . Iodine bromide and bromine chloride were prepared as described in literature⁹. Chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methylene chloride acetonitrile (all A.R. grade) were dried over CaCl_2 and distilled from fresh P_2O_5 . Spectroscopic grade benzene, and carbon disulphide were used without further purifications.

Preparation : β -Picoline-iodine was prepared as described¹⁰ previously (Found ; I_2 , 72.0. β -pic- I_2 calcd. for : I_2 , 73.16%). β -Picoline- ICl and - IBr complexes were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of β -picoline and ICl or IBr in carbon tetrachloride or methanol solutions at 0° , and then recrystallised from methanol and dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum. β -pic- ICl , m.p. 56.5° (Found : N, 5.42 ; C, 27.99 ; H, 2.78 ; total halogen, 62.3. Calcd. for : N, 5.47 ; C, 28.1, H, 2.73 ; total halogen, 63%). β -pic- IBr , m.p. 62.5° (Found : N, 4.52 ; C, 23.84 ; H, 2.32 ; total halogen, 68.8. Calcd. for : N, 4.66 ; C, 24.00 ; H, 2.33 ; total halogen, 69%). As the bromine and bromine chloride complexes of β -picoline were found to be very much unstable in the solid state no attempt was made to take the spectra of solid compounds.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Specord 75 IR grating spectrophotometer using KBr window cells. For solutions, path length of the cells varied

from 0.02 to 0.04 mm. All the measurements were made on freshly prepared solutions. The accuracy in the wave numbers was within $\pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectral resolution in the solution spectra was better than 2 cm^{-1} at 3200 cm^{-1} and better than 1 cm^{-1} at $2500\text{-}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Table 1, reporting only those bands which can be clearly distinguished from the solvent background.

The vibrational spectra of solid β -picoline-iodine in mulls are found to be quite different from that of the equimolar solutions of β -picoline and iodine in non-polar solvents, such as carbon tetrachloride

TABLE I—IR SPECTRA (cm^{-1})* OF β -PICOLINE-IODINE IN VARIOUS MEDIA

1:1 β -pic-I ₂ in CCl ₄	1:1 β -pic-I ₂ in CS ₂	1:1 β -pic-I ₂ in CH ₂ Cl ₂	1:1 β -pic-I ₂ in C ₆ H ₆	1:1 β -pic-I ₂ in CHCl ₃	In β -pic	Solid in mull	β -pic-I ₂ in dioxane	Interpretation**
3 084 w	3 087 vw							A' ν (CH)
3 064 m	3 064 m							A' ν (CH)
	3 050 w							A' ν (CH)
3 020 w								A' ν (CH)
2 960 w	2 960 vw							A' Me
2 924 w								A' Me
	2 860 m							A'' sym CH stretch in Me GP
2 743 w								1 250+1 450
2 610 vw								1 380+1 250
	2 500 w							1 260+1 240
1 916 m	1 916 m			1 916vw				1 230+700
1 900 w	1 910 m							988+915
	1 886 w							1 100+785
				1 730 w				1 100+640
1 716 w	1 716 w							1 031+700
		1 600 m	1 600 w			1 600 m	1 600 w	A' ν (CC)
		1 587 s	1 584 m	1 584 w		1 584 m		988+629
		1 580 w	1 580 w			1 580 w	1 580 m	A' ν (CC)
1 480 s	1 480 sh	1 480 s					1 480 w	A' ν (CC, CN)
1 450 w								A'' asym CH bending in Me GP
			1 430 w			1 423 w		452+915
1 416 m								A' ν (CC, CN)
1 384 w	1 384 w	1 386 w						A'' sym CH bending in Me GP
	1 260 w							A' α (CC)
	1 240 w							A' α (CC)
1 223 w								A' β (CH)
1 194 s	1 193 s	1 193 s	1 192 s	1 192 m		1 186 s	1 193 s	A' β (CH)
	1 164 w							700+452
1 127 s	1 127 s	1 128 s	1 126 s	1 127 s		1 122 s	1 126 w	A' β (CH)
1 102 s	1 100 m	1 099 s	1 100 s	1 100 m		1 092 m		A' ϕ (CC)
		1 058 s				1 058 s	1 059 vw	(β -pic ₂ I ⁺)
1 052 s	1 053 s	1 055 s	1 050 s	1 053 s	1 059 m	1 058 s		A' Ring
1 031 w	1 031 w	1 031 w			1 053 s	1 028 s		A' β (CH)
	988 w							A' γ (CH)
	915 w							535+452
			850 s					A'' γ (CH)
		823 sh				824 m	817 vw	(β -pic ₂ I ⁺)
	814 m	815 sh	814 m	813 w	813 w	810 m	805 w	A'' γ (CH)
	785 s	791 s	789 s			791 s	792 s	A' Ring
711 s	711 vw						710 s	A'' γ (CH)
720 s	700 s			695 m	700 sh	686 s	696 s	A'' γ (CH)
		652 m			651 sh	650 s	653 vw	(β -pic ₂ I ⁺)
641 s	641 s	645 s	643 w	642 m	643 s	645 s	645 s	A' X-sensitive
533 w	533 m	533 w	535 w				535 vw	A'' component of e _g of 404
	460 m	456 m			463 m			A'' X-sensitive

* s = strong, w = weak, m = medium, vw = very weak, sh = shoulder,

** β -pic = β -picoline, sym = symmetrical, asym = asymmetrical, GP = group, Me = methyl.

Results and Discussion

The spectral data over the frequency range $400\text{-}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in a range of solvents and in mulls of β -picoline-iodine complex are presented in

and benzene. Solid β -picoline iodine in mulls shows a strong band at 1058 cm^{-1} and another at 650 cm^{-1} and no band is observed at 530 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1). But equimolar solutions of I₂ and

β -picoline in CCl_4 and in CS_2 show bands at $\sim 1053, 640$ and 534 cm^{-1} . Although the shifting

The spectra of β -pic-IBr and β -pic-ICl are identical both in mulls and in non-polar

Fig 1. Composite ir spectra : (—) solid β -pic- I_2 in nujol mull (---) and (-.-) equimolar solution of I_2 and β -picoline in CS_2 .

of the first two bands may be attributed to the solvent effect but the absence of the band at 530 cm^{-1} , which is usually quite strong, cannot be explained. In polar solvents, such as excess of β -picoline, acetonitrile and also in methylene chloride solutions a pair of bands is observed near 1050 cm^{-1} , i.e. at ~ 1050 and 1063 cm^{-1} and also a pair of bands is observed in the vicinity of 640 cm^{-1} . Besides, a band at 530 cm^{-1} is also observed in all the three solvents. The bands at 1058 and 650 cm^{-1} observed in polar solvents and also in mulls correspond to $(\beta\text{-pic}_2\text{-I})^+$ frequencies¹¹. It may be assumed that the complex is ionised^{12, 13} in excess of β -picoline and also in other polar solvents and the additional bands are due to the presence of $(\beta\text{-pic}_2\text{-I})^+$ ion. In non-polar solvents all the observed bands may be accounted for $\beta\text{-pic-I}_2$. In the case of solid $\beta\text{-pic-I}_2$, possibly it undergoes solid state transformations to $(\beta\text{-pic}_2\text{-I})^+ \text{I}_3^-$, like hexamethylenetetramine-iodine complex¹⁴. This is also observed visually as the colour of the solid changes from orange to dark brown. Moreover, the spectra of the solid compound in mulls are identical to that of the $(\beta\text{-pic}_2\text{-I})^+$ in $(\beta\text{-pic}_2\text{-I}) \text{BF}_4$ (Ref. 11). Further evidence for the formation of I_3^- ion in the solid state is obtained by taking the uv spectra of solid β -picoline-iodine complex showing an intense band at $\sim 363 \text{ nm}$ ^{14, 15}. This band is identified as $\pi_g - \delta_u$ transition for the I_3^- ion. In methylene chloride solution, it gives two bands at ~ 363 and 504 nm . The latter being the blue-shifted iodine band.

In polar solvents, in both the cases, additional bands at ~ 1060 and 551 cm^{-1} are observed but they are generally weak. Assuming the complex is unionised in non-polar media and in mulls and ionised in polar media, all the bands are accounted for. Similar observations are also made for $\beta\text{-pic-Br}_2$ and $\beta\text{-pic-BrCl}$ complexes. In all the cases the spectra of freshly prepared solutions may be entirely accounted for by the equilibria,

Assignments: The bands found in the unionised compounds may be readily assigned by comparing with the spectra of β -picoline¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The symmetry point group of β -picoline is C_s if the methyl group is regarded as point mass. By comparing with the compounds of pyridine and γ -picoline this C_s point group may be assumed to retain by the β -picoline-halogen complexes also. The infra-red data support the C_s symmetry.

For C_s symmetry, the vibration fall into two groups A' and A'' and the 42 fundamental vibrations fall into the classes $29A' + 13A''$; of these vibrations, $4A' + 2A''$ comprises of five intermolecular modes and the halogen-halogen stretching vibrations and they are expected to fall in the far-infrared region. Table 2 which shows the assignments for the observed bands of the complexes, also includes those for the β -picoline. The β -picoline bands at ~ 1044 and 785 cm^{-1} which we have assigned as ring modes donot agree with the assignments made

TABLE 2 - ASSIGNMENT OF FUNDAMENTAL VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF β -PICOLINE COMPLEXES AND COMPARISON WITH β -PICOLINE

Designation	β -pic	β -pic-I ₂	β -pic-IBr	β -pic-ICl	β -pic-Br ₂	β -pic-BrCl
A'						
ν (CH)	3 087	3 087	3 087	3 097	3 093	
ν (CH)	3 050	3 060	3 067	3 066	3 067	3 073
ν (CH)	3 030		3 017	3 030	3 035	3 020
ν (CH)	2 995	3 010	2 997	3 000	2 985	
Me	2 950	2 960	2 950	2 950	2 950	
Me	1 927	1 916	1 923	1 932	1 950	1 916
ν (CC)	1 595	1 600	1 601	1 603	1 600	1 604
ν (CC)	1 577	1 587	1 580	1 580	1 580	1 586
ν (CC, CN)	1 480	1 480	1 480	1 480	1 480	1 483
ν (CC, CN)	1 413	1 416	1 423	1 440	1 410	1 416
β (CH)	1 341		1 345	1 347	1 337	
β (CH)	1 332		1 336	1 336	1 332	1 330
β (CH)	1 226	1 233	1 234	1 241	1 223	1 236
β (CH)	1 194	1 189	1 195	1 197	1 190	1 192
β (CH)	1 126	1 122	1 126	1 130	1 128	1 129
ϕ (CC)	1 108	1 095	1 100	1 100	1 106	1 102
Ring	1 044	1 050	1 057	1 060	1 065	1 063
β (CH)	1 031	1 032	1 031	1 031	1 031	1 033
γ (CH)	985	988	990	990	985	990
Ring	785	788	785	785	785	793
X-sen	629	645	648	649	649	649
A''						
Asym CH stretch in Me GP	2 980	2 960	2 923	2 922	2 923	
Sym CH stretch in Me GP	2 868	2 860	2 851	2 850	2 873	
Asym CH bending in Me GP	1 455	1 430			1 460	1 460
Sym CH bending in Me GP	1 383	1 387	1 387	1 387	1 383	1 380
γ (CH)	924	915	924	930	924	
γ (CH)	857	855	857	857		
γ (CH)	711	697	697	710	712	720
Component of e_{2u} of 404	535	535	535	533	533	535
X-sen	452	467	467	468	460	454

by others¹⁵⁻¹⁷. By comparison with the vibrations of pyridine, these two vibrations have been found to be quite similar to the vibrations 992 and 605 cm^{-1} of pyridine which shifts to higher frequencies on complex formation with halogens.

Effect of environment: As the polarity of the environment increases the transfer of charge from the donor to the acceptor should also increase¹. As a result, the shifts of the vibration frequencies of the β -picoline should increase. This is actually observed in all the complexes for the $\sim 1\,044$ and 629 cm^{-1} bands. It is obvious from Table 2 that the frequency shifts of the $1\,044$ and 629 cm^{-1} bands are dependent on a common factor, and should be directly related to each other. Fig. 2 shows the plots of $1\,044\text{ cm}^{-1}$ against 629 cm^{-1} bands for the complexes β -pic-ICl and β -pic-IBr in a variety of environments. This is also observed for the different complexes Fig. 2.

Frequency shift: With the change of acceptor, the $1\,044$ and 629 cm^{-1} bands of β -picoline shift to different positions. There seems to be no correlation between the extent of the adjacent coordination

atom. The explanation may be given in terms of charge-transfer from the ring to the acceptor.

The charge-transfer takes place from the nitrogen $2sp^2$ lone-pair orbital to the vacant np_x antibonding orbital of halogen, thereby modifying the π -bonding of the ring. This transfer of charge should increase with the increase in acid strength of halogen¹. The acid strength in order of increasing strength are $\text{Cl}_2 \ll \text{Br}_2 < \text{I}_2 \ll \text{IBr} \ll \text{BrCl} \ll \text{ICl}$. This has been observed in the case of dioxane-halogen complexes⁶. But in our case a slight drift is observed. It is observed that the change in frequency is greater for ICl complex than for IBr, which is even greater for I_2 complexes. It is also found to be greater for the BrCl than for the Br_2 complexes. Since I_2 has a greater acid-strength than Br_2 , it is expected that the shift of $1\,044$ or 629 cm^{-1} band will be larger for I_2 than for Br_2 complex. But in practice, exactly the opposite effect is observed. A possible explanation for this anomaly may be given in terms of a back-transfer of charge from the π_g -antibonding orbital of

Fig. 2. Plot of $\Delta\nu_{1044}$ against $\Delta\nu_{629}$ in a variety of solvents: A(O) β -pic-ICl, B(●) β -pic-IBr, C(□) β -pic-Br₂ and D(Δ) β -pic-I₂.

bromine to the lowest unoccupied π -orbital of β -picoline.

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